

Supplementary material to "Software Development in Startup companies: The Greenfield Startup Model"

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1 Technical debt, potential capability and speed measurement

This appendix discusses how the numerical results related to *potential capability*, *technical debt* and *execution speed* have been obtained to validate the high level relation of the model.

In particular we explain the process we utilized to measure three measures:

- *Potential capability*: a metric that represents the degree to which each company reflected the capability of reaction and flexibility to the dynamic environment during the development process, given by the three categories that (theoretically) mostly affect *speed-up development*.
- *Execution speed*: a metric that represents the development speed of the startup during different phases of the first release, computed by means of a weighted average speed for each phase, by analyzing interview transcripts looking at subcategories of *Speed-up development*.
- *Technical debt*: a metric that represents the extent to which processes are controlled, structured, planned and documented by means of engineering artifacts and practices. It has been computed by means of a weighted average of the debt accumulated in each development phase observing subcategories of *accumulated technical debt*, with consequences on startups' growth.

1.1 Potential capability

To define the last measure - *potential capability* - we quantified characteristics related to three theoretical categories: *team is catalyst of development* (CAT4), *product quality has low priority* (CAT3), and *evolutionary approach* (CAT2). According to the framework, these categories contribute respectively to performance, efficiency and effectiveness - and we want to attest the validity of these relations.

Following the example of the SMS, the procedure has been executed simultaneously in pair on the same screen. When necessary we performed an in-depth review of the transcript¹.

To begin the numerical evaluation, we associated a weight to each category (Table 1), reflecting the importance according to the empirical data. Factors related to the team have the largest impact on the score (0.5). Factors related to the methodology undertaken are slightly more important (0.3) than quality-related concerns (0.2).

ID	Category	Weight
CAT4	Skilled team is the catalyst of development	0.5
CAT2	Evolutionary approach	0.3
CAT3	Product quality has low priority	0.2

Table 1: Capability - Weights

¹If the conflicts persisted after an in-depth review of the transcript, we let a third expert person (i.e. our supervisors) take the final decision.

Subsequently we evaluated the three categories separately, assigning a score to each company according to relevant subcategories². In the next subsections we present the detailed evaluation performed on the three categories. Each subcategory has been evaluated using a discrete scale 0 to 2 where 0 represent a null contribution, 1 is average, and 2 is above the average.

1.1.1 Team factors

Selected subcategories from *team is the catalyst of development (CAT4)*:

- T1: High-impact of CTO background.
 - T2: Very small and co-located development team.
 - T3: Developers have big responsibilities (self-organized).
 - Multi-role and full-stack engineers:
 - T4: Engineers are responsible for marketing/sales/development (flat structure).
 - T5: Generalists developers instead of specialists (full-stack).
 - T6: Skilled developers are essential for high speed.
 - T7: Team works under constant pressure.
 - Limited need of formalities between team-members:
 - T8: Positive impact of high co-location.
 - T9: Previous working experience.
 - T10: Knowing each other before starting the company.
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The results of the evaluation are reported in Table 2, where the *weighted score* has been computed by summing up the individual scores obtained in subcategory, multiplying the value by the weight previously defined and finally normalize it on a scale 1 to 5 in order to be able to make a comparison with the *technical debt* and *execution speed*.

Company	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	T9	T10	Weighted score
C1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2.78
C2	0	1	2	1	2	0	2	1	1	1	2.18
C3	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	1	0	1.39
C4	2	1	2	0	1	2	1	1	1	0	2.18
C5	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1.98
C6	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1.39
C7	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	1.39
C8	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2.78
C9	1	1	2	0	1	1	1	2	2	2	2.58
C10	1	1	1	0	1	2	1	2	1	1	2.18
C11	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	3.37
C12	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	2	2	2.18
C13	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	2	1.59

Table 2: Capability - Team

1.1.2 Development approach factors

Selected subcategories from *Evolutionary approach (CAT2)*:

- E1: Flexibility and Reactiveness are main objectives.
- E2: Build a functioning prototype and iterate on it (MVP).

²We excluded categories equally impacting all companies since contributing 0.

- E3: Progressively roll-out to larger number of people.
- E4: Focus on minimal set of functionalities (suitability).
- E5: Small iterations (release often).
- E6: Find product-market fit as soon as possible.

The results of the evaluation are reported in Table 3.

Company	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	Weighted score
C1	1	1	1	1	2	1	0.83
C2	1	1	0	2	1	1	0.71
C3	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.71
C4	2	2	2	2	2	2	1.43
C5	1	1	1	1	1	2	0.83
C6	2	2	0	2	1	1	0.95
C7	2	2	1	2	2	2	1.31
C8	2	1	2	2	2	2	1.31
C9	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.71
C10	1	0	2	1	2	2	0.95
C11	2	2	2	1	2	2	1.31
C12	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.12
C13	0	0	1	0	1	0	0.24

Table 3: Capability - Evolutionary

1.1.3 Quality factors

Selected subcategories from *Product quality has low priority (CAT3)*:

- Q1: UX is the only important quality.
- Q2: Limited number of suitable functionalities.
- Q3: Users are fault-tolerant in innovative beta products.
- Q4: Efficiency emerges after using the product.
- Q5: Product should be reasonably ready-to-scale.

The results of the evaluation are reported in Table 4.

Company	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Weighted score
C1	1	1	1	1	0	0.32
C2	1	1	1	0	0	0.24
C3	1	0	1	0	0	0.16
C4	2	2	1	1	2	0.63
C5	1	1	1	1	2	0.48
C6	1	1	0	1	0	0.24
C7	2	0	0	0	1	0.24
C8	0	2	1	1	1	0.40
C9	1	1	1	1	0	0.32
C10	1	1	1	1	1	0.40
C11	0	2	0	1	1	0.32
C12	1	0	0	0	1	0.16
C13	1	0	1	0	1	0.24

Table 4: Capability - Quality

Finally the three overall scores for *potential capability* have been computed by summing up the weighted contributions of the three categories. Table 5 show the final scores of *potential capability*.

Company	Potential capability
C1	3.928571429
C2	3.134920635
C3	2.261904762
C4	4.246031746
C5	3.293650794
C6	2.579365079
C7	2.936507937
C8	4.484126984
C9	3.611111111
C10	3.531746032
C11	5.000000000
C12	2.460317460
C13	2.063492063

Table 5: Potential capability

In conclusion, all the operations executed in this appendix had the only scope of attesting the correctness of relations between high-level categories of the framework. Although the scores assigned are subject to researchers personal bias, we executed the whole process in pair, and we provided to other researchers the detailed rubrics and instructions necessities for executing similar evaluations.

1.2 Execution speed and Technical debt

Since both *executions speed* and *technical debt* have been computed by summing up weighted contributions phase by phase, they are presented together. First, the phases have been structured outlining the configuration of the interviews³:

- S1: idea/vision/objectives dissemination
- S2: requirements engineering
- S3: analysis
- S4: architecture design
- S5: coding/debugging
- S6: verification and validation
- S7: deployment
- S8: general project management

Afterwards, for each company we assigned a weight to each phase based on the effort declared by the respondents in the follow-up questionnaire⁴. The weights are shown in Table 6.

Company	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	Sum
C1	0.02	0.08	0.11	0.04	0.23	0.23	0.08	0.23	1
C2	0.02	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.23	0.15	0.15	0.23	1
C3	0.02	0.11	0.04	0.08	0.45	0.06	0.02	0.23	1
C4	0.03	0.13	0.04	0.09	0.53	0.07	0.02	0.09	1
C5	0.03	0.09	0.09	0.13	0.40	0.16	0.02	0.09	1
C6	0.03	0.09	0.09	0.27	0.27	0.09	0.09	0.09	1
C7	0.03	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.44	0.22	0.04	0.09	1
C8	0.03	0.13	0.04	0.09	0.53	0.07	0.02	0.09	1
C9	0.03	0.18	0.09	0.18	0.27	0.09	0.09	0.09	1
C10	0.02	0.14	0.07	0.11	0.25	0.07	0.07	0.27	1
C11	0.02	0.08	0.08	0.12	0.41	0.13	0.07	0.08	1
C12	0.03	0.13	0.13	0.18	0.35	0.07	0.02	0.09	1
C13	0.03	0.12	0.09	0.13	0.34	0.14	0.07	0.09	1

Table 6 – Continued on next page

³Observe how we added a new “phase” that was not present initially in the structure of the interview, but emerged from respondents, which typically started to answer our questions of requirement engineering talking about *how they transmitted the initial idea to other team members*.

⁴For the four companies, which didn’t filled the survey, we used average values, adjusted according to interviews.

Table 6 – Continued from previous page

Company	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	Sum
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Table 6: Weights

Figure 1 is a graphical representation of the weights assigned to each phase presented in Table 6.

Figure 1: Execution speed and Technical debt, by phase

As expected, more importance has been assigned to the implementation phase, which occupied most of time and resources of the company. Afterwards we defined a rubric table with extreme values indication phase by phase, used to assign a score from 1 to 5 to each company, for *execution speed* and *technical debt* (see Table 7).

Idea dissemination (S1)		
Score	Execution speed	Technical debt
1	The vision and objectives formally stated with heavy documentation, which needs to be manually updated.	The vision and objectives are maintained through automatic tools, which promptly inform the team-members.
5	Vision clearly shared among team-members.	Not having any means to share the vision.
Requirements engineering (S2)		
Score	Execution speed	Technical debt
1	The company needs to execute a slow process because of a long list of artifacts and formalized specifications.	Requirements artifacts are complete, up-to-date, accessible, structured, traceable and with shared ownership.
5	Use of highly automated tools and low-precision artifacts to specify the initial list of features/stories.	Features are not documented and shared through oral communication and tacit knowledge.
Analysis (S3)		
Score	Execution speed	Technical debt
1	Complete analysis requires formal processes such as risk analysis, feasibility study, critical evaluation of alternative technologies	Pre-defined modus operandi in view of all possible risky situations, fully documented and up-to-date.
5	The only analysis is conducted by logical thinking and reasoning on possible scenarios.	Lack of minimal risk mitigation strategies, and limiting decision taking.
Design (S4)		
Score	Execution speed	Technical debt
1	Formal architecture analysis with detailed diagrams and extended design documentation.	Complete, traceable and up-to-date architectural design artifacts or rigid use of established framework.

Table 7 – Continued on next page

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5	Little up-front-design supported by well-known framework solutions.	Home-made/No-standard or monolithic architecture design without any support of documentation.
Implementation (S5)		
Score	Execution speed	Technical debt
1	Heavy processes definition with lack of automated/integrated tools and use of out-of-code documentation.	Use of coding standard and clean code accessible by any developer (self-explanatory) with advanced versioning system and task management. Collective ownership and critical decision documented and traceable.
5	Lack of out-of-code documentation to update and minimal workflow guidelines without any bureaucracy and simple high automated/integrated tools (advanced versioning system, online collaborative ticket-management)	Lack of coding standards and documentation of critical parts in and out of code. Lack of any task management and versioning system
Verification and validation (S6)		
Score	Execution speed	Technical debt
1	Systematic and rigorous quality assurance processes.	High industry standard met for extensive automatic testing systems with documented test cases.
5	Highly automatized and quick tests of critical parts of the system only.	Complete lack of both automatic and manual testing systems.
Deployment (S7)		
Score	Execution speed	Technical debt
1	Formal deployment policies with multi-staging system or heavily procedures manually conducted.	Advanced automatic tools or services for multi-staging, easy-to-scale deployment, with a defined documentation for deployment steps.
5	New features directly deployed to production with support of simple and automatic tools.	Manual deployment without any documented procedure to follow.
General project management (S8)		
Score	Execution speed	Technical debt
1	Heavy project management with detailed scheduling, tracing team metrics...	Documented and up-to-date well-defined workflow of activities with support of automatic/online tools.
5	Minimal low-precision tools for task management and internal deadlines for the critical milestones.	Lack of any simple workflow with heavy use of manual tools and oral communications.
Extreme values: 1 = very low; 5 = extremely high		

Table 7: Rubrics for execution speed and technical debt

We used these guidelines to consistently evaluate in pair the companies, based on the data collected during the case study. The rubrics naturally emerged during the process of evaluating the first companies, and were constantly updated throughout the process. In case of disagreement, conflicts were examined in-depth to reach a final consensus, sometimes by consulting interview transcripts.⁵ The results of the evaluation of *execution speed* is shown in Table 8, and for *technical debt* in Table 9.

Company	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	Weighted score
C1	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.022556391
C2	3	4	4	4	3	4	4	5	3.977443609
C3	3	4	4	3	4	4	5	3	3.691729323
C4	4	5	5	5	4	3	3	4	4.17699115
C5	5	4	5	5	4	5	4	4	4.407079646
C6	3	3	5	4	4	4	4	4	3.973451327
C7	4	5	4	4	3	4	5	5	3.778761062
C8	4	3	3	4	5	4	4	5	4.442477876
C9	5	4	5	3	4	4	4	4	3.938053097
C10	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	3.659574468
C11	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	4.732290708
C12	3	4	4	4	4	5	5	5	4.150442478
C13	3	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	3.422812193

Table 8 – Continued on next page

⁵Observe that we tried to define two metrics which can be measured independently from each other and from external factors (team experience, project type, ...). How these factors can influence the amount of accumulated technical debt or the execution speed can vary case by case. However, it is not in the scope of this thesis exploring those relations.

Table 8 – Continued from previous page

Company	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	Weighted score
Average	3.85	4.00	4.15	4.00	3.85	4.15	4.15	4.23	4.03

Table 8: Execution speed

Company	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	Weighted score
C1	2	4	2	4	2	4	4	4	3.052631579
C2	1	2	3	3	3	5	3	3	3.180451128
C3	2	3	1	4	2	4	3	3	2.601503759
C4	3	4	3	4	3	2	4	4	3.362831857
C5	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3.14159292
C6	2	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.061946903
C7	1	2	1	3	3	2	4	4	3.03539823
C8	2	2	2	3	4	1	3	3	3.362831858
C9	2	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	2.796460177
C10	1	2	1	3	2	2	2	2	2.085106383
C11	2	3	3	3	4	2	3	3	3.451701932
C12	2	2	2	3	4	2	3	3	3.115044248
C13	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2.973451327
Average	1.92	2.85	2.23	3.15	3.00	3.16	2.69	3.15	3.02

Table 9: Technical debt

1.3 Statistical tests

Summarizing the results of the dimensions discussed in the previous subsections, we present the results in Table 10. Following, we conducted statistical tests using the analysis of variance to assess the existence of relations between *execution speed*, *potential capability* and *technical debt*.

Company	Execution speed	Potential capability	Technical debt
C1	4.022556391	3.928571429	3.052631579
C2	3.977443609	3.134920635	3.180451128
C3	3.691729323	2.261904762	2.601503759
C4	4.17699115	4.246031746	3.362831857
C5	4.407079646	3.293650794	3.14159292
C6	3.973451327	2.579365079	3.061946903
C7	3.778761062	2.936507937	3.03539823
C8	4.442477876	4.484126984	3.362831858
C9	3.938053097	3.611111111	2.796460177
C10	3.659574468	3.531746032	2.085106383
C11	4.732290708	5.000000000	3.451701932
C12	4.150442478	2.46031746	3.115044248
C13	3.422812193	2.063492063	2.973451327

Table 10: Quantification results of *execution speed*, *technical debt* and *potential capability*

First we defined two null hypotheses (H_0): $H_{01} = \text{Startups do not release the product faster when a capable team adopt a more evolutionary approach AND with less quality constraints}$; $H_{02} = \text{The execution speed does not increase the amount of accumulated technical debt}$. Then we tested H_{01} and H_{02} with an one-tailed test using Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient, with positive association analysis, fixing the level of confidence to 95% which means we reject H_0 in case the p-value is lower than 0.05.

We concluded that, in our sample:

1. Higher values of *Execution speed* are strongly associated with *higher* values for *Technical debt* (with a clear statistical significance, p-value: 0.002073).
2. Higher values of *Execution speed* are strongly associated with *higher* values for *Potential capability* (with a clear statistical significance, p-value: 0.004549).

To perform the Pearson's correlation we verified two assumptions: a) data is on interval scale; b) data is normally distributed.

In regard to assumption a) there is a considerable disagreement in the literature whether individual *Likert* items can be considered as interval-level data [1] [2]. However, we provide a symmetric *Likert scale* with a middle category and clearly defined linguistic qualifiers for each item (with the aid of the theoretical framework and rubrics, presented respectively in subsections 1.1 and 1.2). Then, we made our best to present evaluations that are homogeneously (with same interpretation) distributed across the different companies data. Furthermore we improved the approximation of an interval-level measurement by adjusting weights of scores of categories to equally space the 'distance' between the final scores with the use of validated follow-up questionnaire results.

In regard to assumption b) we validated it by conducting the *Kolmogorov-Smirnov* (K-S) test. Each dimension has been tested separately, comparing them with a normal distribution with the same mean and standard deviation. The output gives the output statistic deviation (D) and then a p-value associated with that statistic. Moreover each dimension's distribution is presented by a histogram and respective normal curve.

Figure 2: Distribution of *potential capability*

The output of the *potential capability* K-S test is: $D = 0.1117$, p-value: 0.9909.

Figure 3: Distribution of execution speed

The output of the *execution speed* K-S test is: $D = 0.1223$, p-value: 0.9769.

Figure 4: Distribution of *technical debt*

The output of the *technical debt* K-S test is: $D = 0.2214$, p-value: 0.4799. As shown above in all the cases the p-values are well above 0.05, so we accept that there is no difference between the observations and a set of random observations drawn from a perfect normal distribution with the same mean and variance.

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